

CALCULATION OF THE PAYLOAD TO COMBAT UAVS

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In modern conditions of warfare, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are becoming an increasingly serious threat to the allied infrastructure, manpower and equipment. Cheap attack UAVs, created from civilian components and capable of being manufactured in the field, stand out in particular. For example, the events on the night of January 5-6, 2018 in Syria, at the Khmeimim airbase, showed the degree of threats and the level of damage caused by the raid of such UAVs. As a result, special requirements are put forward for the developed countermeasures, such as low cost and technical simplicity.

The existing weapons of the Russian Federation are capable of fighting the UAVs described above, however, two factors can be attributed to the disadvantages:

- 1) the cost of existing funds (missiles of the 9K330 «Tor» and 96K6 «Pantsir» complexes cost from several tens of millions of rubles);
- 2) the fragmentation warhead of the previously designated missiles is designed to hit large targets, which is achieved by increasing the size of each fragment, but leads to a decrease in the density of the fragmentation field.

This article discusses the modeling and calculation of a missile warhead for destroying unmanned aerial vehicles. The proposed warhead is part of a missile system of a "new" concept (unguided missiles, characterized by cheapness and technical simplicity) and at the same time eliminates the disadvantages of existing warheads. This is achieved by using ready-made fragments, which reduces the cost of production, and also increases the density of the fragmentation field by using a large number of these fragments (due to their small size).

The required number of damaging elements (shots) is calculated. Suppose that to destroy a UAV of any kind, it is enough to hit $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ of its area. Thus, if at least

one shot hits 0,01 m² of the area, the probability of damage is 100%. The Ministry of Defense of the Russian Federation adopts products that guarantee a 95% chance of destroy a target. Therefore, the confidence probability used for calculations is 96%, in which case the area required for "coverage" will increase slightly:

$$\frac{0,01}{x} = \frac{96\%}{100\%} \Rightarrow x = 0,01 * 100 / 96 = 0,0104 \text{ m}^2$$

The idea is that the affected area is represented as a sphere with a certain radius. The formula for the surface area of a sphere:

$$S = 4 * \Pi * R^2, \text{ where } R \text{ is the radius of the sphere}$$

Knowing the surface area of the sphere, it is possible to determine how many damaging elements are needed to cover the area with a given probability level, the idea is presented in Figure 1.

The formula for the required number of damaging elements:

$$N = \frac{4 * \Pi * R^2}{x}, \text{ where } x \text{ is the area of the required coverage}$$

In Figure 1:

Дробины (поражающие элементы) – Shots (damaging elements)

Элементарная площадь, в которую должен попасть хотя бы 1 элемент при интересующем R сферы (зона поражения). Идея заключается в подсчете количества таких зон, помещающихся на площади поверхности сферы – An elementary area that should contain at least 1 element of the interest sphere with the radius R (the affected area). The idea is to count the number of such zones that fit on the surface area of the sphere

Необходимая зона поражения составляет 5/8 от сферы – The required damage area is 5/8 of the sphere

Fig.1 – A sphere with mapped sites (the affected area) and a fraction of the sphere affecting the shots consumption (highlighted in light)

The affected area cannot be a sphere, since the warhead is carried by the rocket body, therefore, the required surface area of the coating is a certain fraction of the total surface area of the sphere, for example, a fraction of 5/8, Figure 1. Using the Microsoft Excel package, Table 1 was formed with calculations of the required mass of damaging elements to cover elementary sites measuring 0.01 m^2 . It is taken into account that the affected area is 5/8 of the surface area of the sphere, and the probability of damage is 96%.

Table 1 – Required mass of damaging elements in grams

(96% probability of damage, elementary sites measuring 10 cm * 10 cm)

	Диаметр дроби, мм	2	2,5	3	3,5	4	4,5	5	5,6	6,2
	Масса одной дробины, грамм	0,049	0,093	0,161	0,256	0,371	0,555	0,74	1,032	1,401
Радиус поражения, м	1	37	70	121	193	280	418	558	778	1 056
	2	148	280	485	772	1 118	1 673	2 231	3 111	4 223
	3	332	631	1 092	1 736	2 516	3 764	5 019	6 999	9 502
	4	591	1 121	1 941	3 087	4 473	6 692	8 923	12 443	16 893
	5	923	1 752	3 033	4 823	6 990	10 456	13 942	19 443	26 395
	6	1 329	2 523	4 368	6 945	10 065	15 057	20 076	27 998	38 009
	7	1 809	3 434	5 945	9 453	13 700	20 494	27 326	38 108	51 734
	8	2 363	4 485	7 765	12 347	17 893	26 768	35 690	49 774	67 571
	9	2 991	5 677	9 828	15 627	22 646	33 878	45 171	62 995	85 519
	10	3 693	7 008	12 133	19 292	27 959	41 825	55 766	77 772	105 579

In Table 1:

Радиус поражения, м – Radius of destroy, m

Диаметр дроби, мм – Diameter of one shot, mm

Масса одной дробины, грамм – Mass of one shot, grams

For greater clarity, the data from the table is presented as a surface with appropriate explanations, Figure 2. Microsoft Excel was used to build the surface.

In Figure 2:

Зависимость массы поражающих элементов от радиуса зоны поражения и диаметра одной дробины (вероятность 96%, площадка 0,01 / 0,04 м²) – Dependence of the mass of the damaging elements on the radius of the affected area and the diameter of one pellet (96% probability, 0,01 / 0,04 m² area)

Необходимая масса поражающих элементов, грамм – Required mass of damaging elements, grams

Радиус зоны поражения, м – Radius of destroy's zone, m

Диаметр одной дробины, мм – Diameter of one shot, mm

Fig.2 – Surfaces constructed based on the results of calculations for different sizes of the affected area

The tables presented contain information on the total mass of damaging elements (shots) of various diameters and masses, with different confidence probabilities of damage and various elementary sites, which are guaranteed to be destroyed.

At the same time, the data obtained make it possible to estimate the ratio of warhead parameters, at which the warhead is absolutely unsuitable for the task being solved. For example, the mass of the damaging elements = 300 kg brings the missile closer to the ballistic class – this is a clear discrepancy with the main idea of the missile armament being developed.

In order to identify the mass of damaging elements that will satisfy the idea of the complex being developed, the table has been supplemented. Namely, a row has been added containing information about the size of the elementary area (watch Table 2).

Table 2 – Updated table of the total mass of the damaging elements for a 96% probability of being hit by a missile

	Сторона элементарного квадрата, см	2	4	6	10	10	12	12	16	20
	Диаметр дроби, мм	2	2,5	3	3,5	4	4,5	5	5,6	6,2
	Масса одной дробины, грамм	0,049	0,093	0,161	0,256	0,371	0,555	0,74	1,032	1,401
Радиус поражения, м	1	923	438	337	193	280	290	387	304	264
	2	3 693	1 752	1 348	772	1 118	1 162	1 549	1 215	1 056
	3	8 308	3 942	3 033	1 736	2 516	2 614	3 485	2 734	2 376
	4	14 771	7 008	5 392	3 087	4 473	4 647	6 196	4 861	4 223
	5	23 079	10 951	8 426	4 823	6 990	7 261	9 682	7 595	6 599
	6	33 234	15 769	12 133	6 945	10 065	10 456	13 942	10 937	9 502
	7	45 235	21 463	16 514	9 453	13 700	14 232	18 976	14 886	12 933
	8	59 082	28 034	21 570	12 347	17 893	18 589	24 785	19 443	16 893
	9	74 776	35 480	27 299	15 627	22 646	23 526	31 369	24 607	21 380
	10	92 316	43 803	33 703	19 292	27 959	29 045	38 727	30 380	26 395

In Table 2:

Радиус поражения, м – Radius of destroy, m

Сторона элементарного квадрата, см – The side of the elementary square, cm

Диаметр дроби, мм – Diameter of one shot, mm

Масса одной дробины, грамм – Mass of one shot, grams

The data obtained makes it possible to identify the most relevant and "interesting" variants of the total mass of damaging elements. They also demonstrate one of the analysis methods that allows changing the characteristics of the warhead and obtaining a different design and layout scheme of the missile.

Thus, the following characteristics are selected for further calculation:

- 1) the probability of UAV's destroys = 96%;
- 2) the elementary square that guarantees the destroy of UAVs = 4 cm * 4 cm;
- 3) the radius of the affected area = 3 meters;

- 4) the diameter of the one shot = 2,5 mm;
- 5) the mass of one shot = 0,093 grams;
- 6) total mass of shots (damaging elements) = 3942 grams.

The approximate speed that the shots should reach after detonating the warhead at a distance of 3 meters from the detonation point (the radius of the guaranteed destroy zone) may be the speed of the shotgun when fired from a shotgun. Shotguns are quite effective at destroying UAVs, quadcopters and drones. The main thing is that the UAV is close to the shooter, otherwise the shot simply will not hit the drone.

The distance from the shooter to the UAV at the time of destruction is 10 m, therefore, the speed of the shotgun blast is enough to destroy the drone [5]. Open sources contain a lot of information about the speed of the shots after the shot, which are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 – Drop in shots velocity when fired (initial velocity $V_0 = 375$ m/s)

Диаметр дроби в мм	1,75	2,0	2,25	2,5	2,75	3,0	3,5	4,0	5,0	6,0	8,0
№ дроби	10	9	8	7	6	5	3	1	0000	Картечь	
Дистанция в м	Скорость дроби в м/сек										
5	332	337	341	344	346	348	352	354	356	358	361
10	285	293	300	306	311	315	321	326	333	338	345
15	28	259	269	276	283	288	297	304	316	322	332
20	218	231	242	251	259	266	277	285	298	308	320
25	196	209	220	230	239	246	258	268	284	296	311
30	174	187	199	210	221	230	245	256	271	283	300
35	156	170	183	194	204	213	228	240	258	272	290
40	139	154	167	178	189	199	215	228	248	261	281
50	106	125	140	153	164	174	191	205	227	243	264
60	86	102	116	129	141	151	168	183	208	225	248

In Table 3:

Диаметр дроби, мм – Diameter of one shot, mm

№ номер дроби – Shot's number

Картечь – Buckshot

Дистанция в м – Distance in meters

Скорость дроби в м/сек – Velocity of shot in m per sec

To solve this problem, we will use the formulas given in the laboratory workshop of the disciplines "Striking effect" and "Effectiveness of missile systems" by S. N. Yeltsin, the necessary formulas are given below:

$$1) V_p = 0.5D \sqrt{\frac{\varphi_1 \alpha}{2+4\alpha/\varphi}} - \text{the initial velocity of fragmentation of shots, where } D$$

is the detonation velocity of the explosive, φ – coefficient that takes into account the shape of the warhead ($\varphi = 3,33$ for a spherical shape), φ_1 – coefficient that takes into account the loss of energy going to the destruction of the shell or to the breakthrough of detonation products into the gaps of finished fragments and transmitted by fragments to the air at the time of separation ($\varphi_1 = 0,95$ for the warhead under development);

2) $\alpha = \frac{m_{\text{BBi}}}{m_{\text{M}}}$ – coefficient, where m_{BBi} – the mass of the explosive substance falling on the shots of the i -th belt, m_{M} – the mass of shots in the i -th belt;

3) $V_R = V_0 \exp\left(-C_x \frac{\rho S_{\text{cp}} R}{2m}\right)$ – the velocity of the fragment at a distance R from the detonation point, where C_x – coefficient of aerodynamic drag of the shot, ρ – air density, S_{cp} – characteristic area of the shot.

First, let's calculate what the initial velocity of the shots should be, so that the speed at a distance of 3 meters is 300 m/s. The solution uses code written in MatLab:

```
R=3; %расстояние от точки подрыва (радиус зоны поражения), м
r=(2.5/2)/1000; %радиус дробины, м
S=pi*r^2; %характерная площадь дробины
p=1.23; %плотность атмосферы, кг/м^3
Cx=0.4; %аэродинамический коэффициент для шара
m=0.093/1000; %масса одной дробины, кг
Vr=300; %необходимая скорость на границе зоны поражения, м/с

V0=Vr/exp((-Cx*p*S*R)/(2*m));
```

V0 =
311.9166

In this code:

Расстояние от точки подрыва (радиус зоны поражения), м – Distance from the detonation point (radius of the affected area), m

Радиус дробины, м – Radius of the shot, m

Характерная площадь дробины – Characteristic area of the shot

Плотность атмосферы, кг/м³ – Atmospheric density, kg/m³

Аэродинамический коэффициент для шара – Aerodynamic coefficient for the ball

Масса одной дробины, кг – Mass of one shot, kg

Необходимая скорость на границе зоны поражения, м/с – Required speed at the boundary of the affected area, m/s

For further calculations, the required initial velocity of the destroying fragment (shot) is assumed to be 312 m/s.

The main task of this section is to find the required explosive mass in the warhead of the missile being developed. Analyzing the method used in laboratory practice, you can calculate everything you need. The data required for the calculation is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Explosive detonation rates

Explosives	Detonation velocity, m/s
Smoky powder	400
Pyroxylin (with 13% N)	6300
Nitroglycerin	7450
Rattlesnake Jelly	7800
Gurdinamite (with 75% nitroglycerin)	6650
Rattlesnake mercury	6500
Picric acid	7100
Trinitrotoluene	6700
Trinitrobenzene	7000
Trinitrocresol	6850
Tetril	7200
Ammonal	5400

From the above formulas 1 and 2, we derive the following formula for calculating the mass of explosives:

$$m_{BB} = \frac{2 \left(\frac{V_p}{0.5D} \right) \varphi m_M}{\varphi_1 \varphi - 4 \left(\frac{V_p}{0.5D} \right)^2}$$

To automate the calculation, we create the code in MatLab:

```
%СКОРОСТИ ДЕТОНАЦИИ ТВЕРДЫХ ВВ
D1=400; %дымный порох, м/с
D2=5400; %аммонал, м/с
D3=6300; %пироксилин, м/с
D4=7000; %тротил, м/с
D5=7200; %тетрил, м/с
D6=7800; %гремучий студень, м/с

%ОСТАЛЬНЫЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЯ
Mm=3942/1000; %полная масса осколков, кг
F1l=0.95; %коэф. потерь энергии на прорыв оболочки
F1=3.33; %коэф. формы БЧ (сфера)
Vp=312; %потребная скорость осколков, м/с

%РАСЧЕТНАЯ ФОРМУЛА ПОЛНОЙ МАССЫ ВВ

Skobka=Vp/(0.5*D6);
Chislitel=2*F1*Mm*Skobka^2;
Znamenatel=F1l*F1 - (4*(Skobka^2));

Mbb=Chislitel/Znamenatel;
```


Command Window
New to MATLAB? See resources for [Getting Started](#).

```
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = -9.7233
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = 0.1127
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = 0.0824
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = 0.0666
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = 0.0629
>> MassOfVV
Mbb = 0.0535
```

In this code:

Скорости детонации твердых ВВ – Detonation speeds of solid explosives

Дымный порох, м/с – Smoky powder, m/s

Аммонал, м/с – Ammonal, m/s

Пироксилин, м/с – Pyroxylin, m/s

Тротил, м/с – TNT, m/s

Тетрил м/с – Tetril, m/s

Гремучий студень, м/с – Rattlesnake jelly, m/s

Остальные значения – Other values

Полная масса осколков, кг – Total mass of shots, kg

Коэф. потерь энергии на прорыв оболочки – Coefficient of energy loss for shell destroying

Коэф. формы БЧ (сфера) – Coefficient of warhead shape (sphere)

Потребная скорость осколков, м/с – Required velocity of shots, m/s

Расчетная формула полной массы ВВ – The calculation formula for the total mass of explosives

Table 5 shows the required masses of explosives of various types (solid state of aggregation). It is worth noting that using smoky powder, it is impossible to achieve the desired result.

Table 5 – Required mass of explosive for using in missile

Name of solid explosive	Required initial velocity of shots	Total mass of shots	Required mass of explosive, grams
Smoky powder	312 m/s	3942 grams	-
Ammonal			113
Pyroxylin			83
TNT			67
Tetril			63
Rattlesnake jelly			53

The following are the clarifying calculations of the missile warhead.

The concept of the ammunition filling coefficient is introduced, which shows the ratio of the explosive mass and the total mass of the ammunition:

$$\alpha = \frac{\omega}{m} = \frac{\omega}{n + \omega}$$

α is the filling coefficient.

ω is the mass of the explosive substance, kg.

m is the total mass of the ammunition, kg.

n is the mass of the damaging elements (shots), kg.

It becomes possible to calculate the local filling coefficient ξ , which takes into account the useless mass. In a simplified form, the useless mass, from the point of view of the formation of fragments, is the mass of the explosive device:

$$\xi = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \mu} = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \frac{m_{BY}}{m}}$$

m_{BY} – mass of the explosive device, kg.

Now it is possible to calculate the initial velocity of the fragments (shots / buckshot) using the formula:

$$v_0 = \frac{D}{2} * \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{2 - \alpha}}$$

v_0 is initial velocity of shot, m/s.

D is detonation speed of explosive, m/s.

Previously identified patterns show that the required initial velocity of the fragment should be at least 375 m/s. For additional assurance, we will assume a required speed of 400 m/s.

The main task, in our case, is to calculate the required explosive mass. Therefore, the formulas used need to be transformed somewhat:

$$v_0 = \frac{D}{2} * \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{2 - \alpha}} = \frac{D}{2} * \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{m_{BY}}{m}}{2 - \alpha}} = \frac{D}{2} * \sqrt{\frac{\omega}{\left(1 - \frac{m_{BY}}{n + \omega}\right) * \left(2 - \frac{\omega}{n + \omega}\right) * (n + \omega)}}$$

v_0 is the initial velocity of shots, m/s.

D is detonation speed of explosive, m/s.

ω is the mass of the explosive, kg.

m_{BY} is the mass of the explosive device, kg.

n is the mass of the damaging elements, kg.

To simplify the calculations, we use the code written in MatLab:

§Расчет боевой части		Name ▲	Value
D1 = 400; %скорость детонации дымного пороха, м/с		Alpha	0.0478
D2 = 6300; %скорость детонации пироксилина, м/с		D1	400
D3 = 7450; %скорость детонации нитроглицерина, м/с		D2	6300
D4 = 7100; %скорость детонации пикриновой кислоты, м/с		D3	7450
D5 = 6700; %скорость детонации тринитротолуола, м/с		D4	7100
D6 = 7000; %скорость детонации тринитробензола, м/с		D5	6700
D7 = 6850; %скорость детонации тринитрокрезолола, м/с		D6	7000
D8 = 7200; %скорость детонации тетрила, м/с		D7	6850
D9 = 5400; %скорость детонации аммонала, м/с		D8	7200
		D9	5400
Omega = 0.2; %масса взрывчатого вещества, кг		Ksi	0.0490
n = 3.98; %масса поражающих элементов, кг		M_Full	4.1800
mvu = 0.1; %масса взрывательного устройства, кг		mvu	0.1000
		n	3.9800
M_Full = n + Omega; %полная масса боеприпаса, кг		Nyu	0.0239
Alpha = Omega / M_Full; %коэффициент наполнения		Omega	0.2000
Nyu = mvu / M_Full; %коэффициент бесполезной массы		V1	31.6926
Ksi = Alpha / (1-Nyu); %местный коэффициент наполнения		V2	499.1586
		V3	590.2748
V1 = (D1/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V4	562.5438
V2 = (D2/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V5	530.8512
V3 = (D3/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V6	554.6206
V4 = (D4/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V7	542.7359
V5 = (D5/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V8	570.4669
V6 = (D6/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с		V9	427.8502
V7 = (D7/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с			
V8 = (D8/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с			
V9 = (D9/2) * sqrt(Ksi/(2 - Alpha)) %начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с			

In this code:

Скорость детонации дымного пороха – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации пироксилина – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации нитроглицерина – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации пикриновой кислоты – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации тринитротолуола – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации тринитробензола – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации тринитрокрезола – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации тетрила – Detonation speeds of

Скорость детонации аммонала – Detonation speeds of

Масса взрывчатого вещества, кг – Mass of explosive, kg

Масса поражающих элементов, кг – Mass of shots, kg

Масса взрывательного устройства, кг – Mass of explosive device, kg

Полная масса боеприпаса, кг – Total mass of ammunition, kg

Коэффициент наполнения – Filling coefficient

Коэффициент бесполезной массы – Coefficient of the useless mass

Местный коэффициент наполнения – Local filling coefficient

Начальная скорость разлета осколков, м/с – Initial velocity of shots, m/s

Below is table 6 with the initial data and the calculation result.

Table 6 – Research result

Explosives	Detonation velocity, m/s	Required explosive mass, grams	Initial velocity of shots, m/s
			Calculation
Smoky powder	400	-	-
Pyroxylin (with 13% N)	6300	83	645,84
Nitroglycerin	7450	59	645,69
Picric acid	7100	65	645,73
Trinitrotoluene	6700	73	645,78
Trinitrobenzene	7000	67	645,74
Trinitrocresol	6850	70	645,76
Tetril	7200	63	645,71
Ammonal	5400	113	646,03

It is not advisable to use some of the calculated explosives in the design, since: nitroglycerin is very sensitive to impact, friction, high temperatures, and sudden heating; trinitrophenol has increased corrosion activity and sensitivity; trinitrobenzene is explosive; smoky powder does not have the necessary energy characteristics. Components such as: trinitrotoluene, trinitrocresol, tetryl and ammonal are acceptable for use in products of this type. The further choice of one of them depends on the

expediency, which is determined by the operating conditions, the technological features of the existing production and the reduction in the cost of the manufactured product.

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